

NIGERIAN MARKET HIGH DENSITY FIBREBOARD (HDF) FLEXURAL STRENGTH EVALUATION

¹*Chukwudi Paulinus Ilo, ²Sandra Ngozi Nneji and ³Goodchild Alo Igede

¹Department of Mechanical and Production Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, P.M.B. 01660, Enugu, Nigeria.

²Physical Planning Unit, Enugu State Universal Basic Education Board (ENSUBEB), Enugu, Nigeria.

³Engineering Department, Ebonyi State Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: chukwudi.ilo@esut.edu.ng/ +234 814 643 8802

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Abstract: Requisite flexural strength data on high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite in Nigerian market needed by stakeholders to prevent loss of revenue that may be related with the failure from the use of inappropriate high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite for numerous needs because of non-existence of such information was assessed. To establish their bending strength at peak or ultimate bending strength, most frequently sought after were identified, out of which the top three were subjected to test after selection. Each of the samples as required by the testomic machine was prepared and tested. Flexural strength versus the associated strain plots were obtained from data generated with computer program. Results reveal that Joubert (HDF) recorded 15.604 N/mm², Dabar (HDF) recorded 32.604 N/mm² while Sinoply (HDF) recorded 39.248 N/mm² of their flexural strength at peak. Joubert, Dabar and Sinoply recorded their peak flexural strength at 0.2473%, 0.3769% and 0.7979% strain respectively. With its plateau-like peak, Sinoply showed more ductile nature implying less brittle and more resilience to deformation. This knowledge when effectively leveraged can prevent loss of revenue that may be connected with the failure from the use of unsuitable high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite in Nigerian market with respect to their ultimate bending strength as it can be utilized by engineers, building contractors, individuals, construction companies as well as furniture makers. Biomedical device developers can as well tap on this knowledge. Mechanical tests like hardness tests of wood composites in Nigerian market should be the future research interest.

Keyword: Bending Rigidity, Creep, Durability, Elasticity, Flexural Modulus, Flexural Stress, Flexural Strength, Mechanical Test, Modulus of Rupture, Resilience, Rigidity, and Stability.

I. Introduction

Background of the Study

FMRL, (2025) noted that at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) estimate of 4.5%, the global plywood market valued at USD 50.2 billion in 2024 is expected to grow from 2025 with projection to reach USD 74.5 billion by 2033. Exports of forestry products industrial goods in the 1950's, 1960's and 1970's were once

enjoyed by Nigeria as plywood remains a vital engineered wood product extensively used across construction, furniture, and packaging industries in Nigeria (Ogunwusi, 2012). Unfortunately, as at present Nigeria, remains heavily dependent on wood composite (plywood) imports, despite its abundant raw materials and a fast-growing domestic market. Usually obtained through the processes of binding the particles, fibers, strands, or boards of wood together, wood composites are different derivative wood products. Similar composite products can also be made from vegetable fibers using lignin-containing materials with chemical additives enabling the integration of polymer and wood floor while helping facilitate optimal processing conditions. Garcia-Garcia, et al, (2018) noted that such materials could be rye and wheat straw, hemp stalks, sugar cane residue e.t.c. due to an excellent combination of mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties together with a competitive price, particle and fiberboards are widely used in the building industry as eco-friendly solutions to wood with increasing uses in thermal insulators, ceiling boards, wall partitions, etc. It is obviously interesting to note that wood composites can be created using smaller trees, wood waste materials and hence reduce the need to fell old-growth forests. Wood composites are engineered to certain specifications resulting in a material that can have diverse applications achieved using adhesives. Ilo, Ajibo and Dim, (2025a) asserted that failure of form boards frameworks from wood composites (plywood) especially while the concrete is still not yet set shortly after casting of concretes has been a major source of concern to the construction industry. It has been revealed that there is a remarkable improvement of the mechanical properties with combination of the alkali treatment followed by silanization through a study on the production of highly environmentally-friendly fiberboards by hot-press molding with the use of *Posidonia oceanica* wastes and a partially biobased epoxy resin as binder (Garcia-Garcia, et al, 2018). Made from wood fibers that are pressed together with a binding agent, Medium Density Fiberboard (MDF) are dense, flat, and of smooth surface often used for furniture, cabinets and molding. As a result of higher chemical heat content and melting properties, higher fire hazard could be experienced when wood composite is compared to solid wood products. Most cheap and common resins usually used in the composites and made with urea-formaldehyde bonded products release toxic formaldehyde in the finished products forming a strong apprehension with wood composite use. Though the process of their manufacture as it relates to solid timber demands for extra primary energy, wood composites have numerous advantages. Above stated is in addition to the humidity-induced warping which is not common in solid woods by some fiber-based and particle based composite woods when they are exposed to moisture. It is quite stating that demand for wood composite is on the rise as projected by the earlier statistics despite all these stated due to remarkable improvement on mechanical and esthetic properties of the resulting composites.

Igboekulie, Monye and Joseph (2022) noted a very strong relationship has been found to exist between building materials prices and rate of residential development following their quest to assess the effect of building materials cost on housing development in Owerri, Imo state, eastern region of Nigeria. Barguma, et al, (2022) revealed from the study of inflation trend pattern and its impact on Nigeria's economy that the purchasing power of the Nigerian currency, Naira was seen to be decreasing a revelation that the economy especially building materials market is badly hit by the inflation. Obaedo, (2024) while analyzing the inflation rate and the

prices of building materials in Benin City, indicated from a correlation analysis that prices of the building materials had a direct relationship with the inflation rate in Nigeria thus the cause for the high cost of building materials. Thus, inflation was revealed as the most influential factor responsible for increase in the cost of building materials.

Ultimate Bending strength

Flexural strength is an important mechanical property of materials that influence their performance in a lot of aspects. Ultimate flexural strength is an indicator of maximum stress a material is capable of withstanding if it is subjected to bending load. Often linked with modes of failure like breaking, cracking or deforming excessively, is an essential material property. Influenced by four factors of material composition which is the type and arrangement of atoms or molecules in the material; material structure which has to do with porosity, fibre orientation, grain size, implying their internal structure; environmental conditions for example exposure to chemicals, humidity or temperature and surface finish, which is the smoothness or surface roughness flexural strength of materials is very pivotal in their application. Flexural strength application importance covers material selection meaning that understanding flexural strength helps to choose suitable materials for product design and specific applications and structural integrity, where flexural strength is instrumental in designing of structures ranging from beams, buildings and bridges. Again, in design of furniture, equipment like that of sports, and even furniture, flexural strength considerations are of high importance. The three-point bending tests, a common method for measuring flexural strength as well as four-point bending test are the regular testing methods utilized in determining the flexural strength of materials. Bending strength at peak, also known as peak bending strength or modulus of rupture (MOR), is the maximum stress a material can withstand while being bent before rupturing or failing. For various engineering applications where bending loads are significant, like: beams, bridges or structural components, bending strength at peak is critical in designing and evaluating materials like concrete, wood composites (plywood), ceramics etc.

II. Literature Review

The effects of carbonized coconut shell (CS) volume fraction on mechanical properties of unsaturated polyester resin (UPR) composite were studied by (Iloabachie, Obiorah and Anene 2018). The mechanical properties tests results show that flexural strength and elongation at break increased as coconut shell proportion got increased. High mechanical properties, was found when the effect of adding a blend of tannins to commercial urea formaldehyde (UF) on the particleboard made from wood particles of *Acacia seyal* var. *seyal* using the British Standard European Norm (BSEN) relevant standards as compared to the ones produced by solely urea formaldehyde (UF) (Elbadawi, Osman, Paridah, Nasroun and Kantiner 2015). The effect of particle size on the flexural strength, ultimate tensile strength, density and water absorption characteristics of uncarbonized coconut shell/unsaturated polyester composites of particle size 425 microns sample and 170 microns sample was investigated and the result indicated that maximum flexural and ultimate tensile strength were attained at 20wt% for the 425 microns sample (Iloabachie, Iet al, 2017). Ganesan and Valarmathi (2014), studied the tensile strength of Teak Wood Saw Dust – Cashew nut shell liquid resin composites. The composite material

was prepared by using a hand layup technique while samples were prepared by varying the quantity of the Cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) resin and keeping the saw dust quantity constant. The simple methodology was just by increasing the percentage of (CNSL). Tensile strength test on the composites using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) according to the ASTM D638 showed that tensile strength of the sample with the highest percentage of (CNSL) was the highest and that the tensile increased with increase in (CNSL). This implies that increase in the cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) percentage improves the tensile strength of the composite. Ihueze, Achike, and Okafor (2016) observed that coconut fibre reinforced HDPE has 28.6 mega pascal as optimum value for flexural strength while studying performance characteristics and reinforcement combinations of coconut fibre reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) polymer matrixes at optimum condition of volume fractions and particle sizes of coconut fibre-filler. As a result of research recently conducted on experimental analysis of flexural strength of wood composite (plywood) in Nigerian commercial sector some technical data relevant to wide application and every plywood user came up. Ilo, Ajibo, and Dim, (2025b) revealed a novel finding that Viewpoint plywood recorded 4.956 N/mm^2 , Plywood EQ recorded 9.467 N/mm^2 while Caledonian also a make of plywood in Nigerian market recorded 16.973 N/mm^2 as the maximum stress, modulus of rupture (MOR) each of them can withstand while being bent before failing or rupturing.

Iloabachie, et al, (2014) through the study of effects of carbonization on the physical and mechanical properties of coconut shell particle reinforced polyester composite, carbonized coconut shell particle reinforced composite recorded the least density value making it desirable in light weight material application. In a test conducted for the potentials of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) such as plastic films from packaging as resins for saw dust from coconut lumber for the production of wood-plastic composite (WPC) particleboard when the boards were prepared from 50%-80% by weight of LPDE to sawdust content, both physical and mechanical properties of WPC evaluated showed that the tensile strength, face screw holding and modulus of rupture meet the minimum specifications of the US standards according to (Valle, 2020). The study also revealed good interfacial adhesion between sawdust particle and LDPE reduced thickness swelling and improving moisture resistance by diminishing hygroscopy hence expanding the utilization of composites from agricultural wastes and plastic wastes for industrial applications, especially in moist environments, even as well as marine use and humid environment.

Courard, (2012) shows the evolution of surface properties of concrete through measured lightness and absorption was analysed in the study of panel frameworks, and it was found that changes were observed on surface quality after 50 reuses with oriented strand board (OSB) panels formworks while modification of surface quality was noticed after 80 reuses with marine plywood formworks. Okafor, Ihueze, and Nwigbo, (2013) applied Taguchi robust design while studying the optimization of hardness strengths response of plantain fibres reinforced polyester matrix composites (PFRP) and observed that empty fruit bunch fibre reinforced polyester matrix composite has the maximum hardness strength of 19.062 N/mm^2 which depended greatly on the reinforcement combinations of control factors. Akinyemi, Afolayan, and Oluwatobi, (2016) conducted a study on the properties of developed composite corn cob (CC) and sawdust (SD) particle boards using 100%,

75%, 50%, 25% and 0% variations for both agricultural wastes using formaldehyde as binder at constant volume. The study reveals that for both physical and mechanical properties, the result showed that the panels with 50% CC had the most preferred performances.

Ilo, Nwanjoku, and Olayeye (2025) revealed from the study of medium density fibreboard (MDF) wood composite in Nigerian market that SGK Nordic had the best ultimate flexural strength of 13.568 N/mm², Richard Russel had ultimate flexural strength 12.986 N/mm² while MDF Hokusun (MDF) recorded 1.24 N/mm². Ozioko, (2011) revealed that wear behaviours of 9500C carbonized ash were better than those of 8500C and 9000C carbonized ash due to the degree of alteration in the structure of silica upon the analysis of the effect of carbonization temperature on wear rate behaviour of rice husk ash reinforced epoxy composites. While the study was conducted on the influence of activated carbon filler on the mechanical properties of wood composites, higher strength value of medium density fibreboards (MDF) composites samples than plywood composites samples was revealed because of the increasing thickness of the activated carbon filler Aziz, et al, (2015). It is obvious that research has not been directed towards providing technical information on high density fibreboards (HDF) in Nigerian market with regards to flexural strength from the review of related literature, hence the obvious need for this research paper.

III. Research Methodology

Material

From the survey made, most common and three major high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite in top demands were identified in Nigerian market. They were selected as samples for analysis. The high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite samples were Sinoply, Joubert and Dabar. They are represented accordingly in table 1.

In table 1, the samples are marked “e”, “f” and “g” representing Sinoply, Joubert and Dabar respectively. They are all prepared according to the requirement by the machine and tested on the machine one after the other.

TABLE 1: High-Density Fiberboard (HDF) wood composite samples tested

Sample	e	f	g
Make	Sinoply	Joubert	Dabar

Equipment

The testometric testing machine as seen in figure 1 which is a universal testing machine (UTM) is clamping down a sample of high-density fibreboard (HDF) for test. The testometric testing machine moves down in operation to clamp on the material with the jaw on appropriately placed and conditioned high-density fibreboard (HDF). As the jaw moves down, by the resistive potentials of each sample, data on the flexural properties is generated.

Diligently prepared according to the requirement by the testometric machine shown in figure 1, the samples (e) representing Sinoply, (f) representing Joubert and (g) representing Dabar were all tested on the machine one after the other. The materials were prepared by cutting to the dimensions of 30 mm x 200 mm so as to fit in with the testing machine as required. Operated by moving the jaw of the TESTOMETRIC TESTING MACHINE

down to clamp on the workpiece as earlier stated that is the conditioned high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite samples, mechanical properties of the high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite are evaluated during the process. With computer program the dynamics of the stress in N/mm^2 versus strain in % plot for the test is generated from data obtained. Obviously, the plot being a function of the samples compositions resulting from their nature is a clear indication of the relationship between force per unit area and deformation per unit length in a material under load. In this case the material being the high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite. The data generated is analysed under results and analysis below.

Fig. 1: Testometric machine

IV. Results and Analysis

For each of the samples Sinoply, Joubert and Dabar, the results of the tests are shown as plots in figures 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Basically, showing flexural strength in N/mm^2 against strain in (%), the plots are for the tested samples of the three selected high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite.

Plots

The plot below is a graph of flexural strength against strain of figure 2 which gradually sustained a rise from 0 N/mm^2 stress at 0 (%) strain to attain ultimate bending strength of $39.248 N/mm^2$ at strain of 0.7979 % for Sinoply high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite while the testometric testing machine was in operation. The ultimate bending strength value as expected, precedes a decline portion of the plot which is the plastic region. Of course, the plastic region succeeds the elastic region just immediately after ultimate bending strength.

Fig. 2: Graph of flexural strength in N/mm^2 against strain in (%) for Sinoply high-density fiberboard (HDF).

Below is a graph showing the plot of flexural strength against strain of figure 3 which gradually sustained a rise from $0 N/mm^2$ stress at $0 (\%)$ strain to attain ultimate bending strength of $15.604 N/mm^2$ at strain of 0.2473% for Joubert high-density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite while the testometric testing machine was in operation. Again, the ultimate bending strength value as expected, precedes a decline portion of the plot which is the plastic region, while of course the plastic region succeeds the elastic region just immediately after ultimate bending strength.

Fig. 3: Graph of flexural strength in N/mm^2 against strain in (%) for Joubert high-density fiberboard (HDF).

The plot below is a graph of flexural strength against strain of figure 4 sustaining a rise from $0 N/mm^2$ stress at $0 (\%)$ strain to attain ultimate bending strength of $32.604 N/mm^2$ at strain of 0.3769% for Dabar high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite while the testometric testing machine was in operation. It is worthy of note that the ultimate bending strength value as expected, precedes a decline portion of the plot which is the plastic region. Again, just immediately after ultimate bending strength, the plastic region succeeds the elastic region.

Fig 4: Graph of flexural strength in N/mm² against strain in (%) for Dabar high-density fiberboard (HDF).

V. Conclusion and Recommendation

In an ascending order of their ultimate bending strength, results of flexural tests conducted on three common high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite and most widely used from Nigerian market show that, Joubert high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite recorded 15.604 N/mm² at 0.2473% strain, Dabar high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite recorded 32.604 N/mm² at 0.3769% strain while Sinoply high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite recorded 39.248 N/mm² at 0.7979% strain. The plastic region which succeeds the elastic region immediately after ultimate bending stress for Sinoply, is characterised by a state of lack of significant decline, a plateau like phase stretched for a strain range of almost 2.4608 % until a flexural strength of 23.484 N/mm² at strain of 3.2587 % where it experienced a sharp drop in flexural strength. Dabar high-density fiberboard (HDF) is characterised by a very short state of lack of significant decline, a plateau like phase stretched for a short strain range of just 0.0108 % until a flexural strength of 32.346 N/mm² at strain of 0.3877 % where it experienced a sharp drop in flexural strength. This technical insight when properly utilized can ward off financial losses associated with failure from the use of inappropriate high-density fiberboard (HDF) wood composite in Nigerian market with respect to their ultimate bending strength. Engineers, building contractors, individuals, construction companies as well as furniture makers should value this novel technical insight. Biomedical equipment developers can as well tap on this knowledge. Future research works in wood composites should be channelled towards hardness tests of wood composites in Nigerian market.

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